

Error Correction: a Proposal for a Standard

Harold Kirkham¹, Artis Riepnies¹, Eddy So² and Jim McBride³

¹Pacific Northwest National Laboratory
harold.kirkham@pnl.gov

²National Research Council of Canada ³JMX Services, Inc

Abstract — Some of the errors in transducers such as instrument transformers can be corrected as part of the digital processing for the measurement. The instrument transformer can be characterized in such a way that allows the Transducer Electronic Data Sheet of IEEE Std 1451 to transfer the information to the measurement system. A modification would allow the measurement system to perform a high-quality self-calibration whenever a transducer was replaced. That levies requirements on the characterization accuracy of the instrument transformer.

Index Terms — Transducer Electronic Data Sheet, transducer error, self-calibration, error correction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Measurement connects the physical world to a conceptual model: an equation. In a moving coil instrument, the “equals sign” is manifested by the balance of the torque generated by the current in the coil against the torque of a return spring. In a digital instrument, the equation solving is more obvious. The equation being solved is the measurand. It was shown in [1] that the notion that measurement is equation-solving has many useful consequences. The simplifications and approximations of linguistic labeling are done away with: a concrete definition is readily found for measurands that have been problematical in the past—frequency, for example, when frequency is changing. The residuals can be used to calculate a metric that indicates the quality of the measurement.[2]

In this paper, we use the notion that the measurand is a model, an equation, to examine high voltage measurement.

II. MEASUREMENT FRAMEWORK

The measurement framework, drawn as a block diagram, establishes the relationships between parts of the measurement process well known to metrologists. It can also be drawn to show the transducers used, as in Figure 1. In the figure, the solid arrows represent physical links, the open arrows conceptual ones. Figure 1 shows a measurement system such as a phasor measurement unit (PMU), in which the measuring instrument is made as accurate as required, and calibrated from its input terminals. In use, the measurement result will inevitably contain the artifacts added by the transduction system, typically using instrument transformers (IT).

Fig. 1. Measurement framework, with transducer included

Applied to high voltage measurement, an isolation transformer, a CCVT or some active system based on field measurement may be involved. The point is that the primary quantity (the thing of concern to the application) is separated from the measuring instrument. The realized quantity is supposedly a scaled copy of the original, but the scaling will be imperfect, to a greater or lesser degree.

III. CHANGING THE EQUATION

The artifacts of the transducer that cause differences from perfect scaling are generally known as the cause of Type B uncertainties. In particular, the scale factor could be off-nominal, and there will be some frequency-response effects. These uncertainties are generally characterized during calibration tests.

For high voltage and current measurements, instrument transformers (IT) are commonly used, with specified “accuracy class.” Both IEC and IEEE specify the relationship between ratio error and phase error graphically. The IEC standard [3] shows the boundary of the permitted region by rectangular boxes on a plane of ratio error vs phase error for each IT accuracy class without restrictions on the range of their load power factor. The IEEE standard [4] uses parallelogram boxes to describe their accuracy class, with the load power factor being limited within the range of 0.6 to 1.0. There are proposals to change the IEEE standard to the “square box” accuracy classes.

It is proposed that at least some of these artifacts can be compensated for by changing the solution method in the measurement algorithm. Calibration data for the transducer can be added to the information available to the algorithm, and

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a solution found for the measurand that more closely represents the primary quantity. That could put the result of the measurement well *inside* the uncertainty box.

Consider the example of the PMU. The PMU produces four parameters in its result. It assumes the signal is sinusoidal, and gives the amplitude, frequency, phase (with respect to a well-defined reference) and the rate of change of frequency.

While devices are made that demonstrate extremely accurate results during lab testing, no allowance is made for the errors that may exist in the IT.

The requirements levied [5] on the PMU limit the uncertainty of the amplitude and the phase results, which are referred to as the *synchrophasor*. The standard combines the allowed error on these parameters in a vector fashion that is tantamount to an upper limit of about the same magnitude as that of the IT. In other words, a compliant PMU and a compliant IT may produce a non-compliant result.

Correcting for the errors would allow improved system analyses. The idea is not new. Passive correction was applied as long ago as 1912 [6] to reduce amplitude errors. In 1991, an active electronic system was demonstrated as a range extender [7] with low errors over a wide frequency range. An on-line system was simulated [8] in 2000. A system of correcting for errors that were temperature dependent was simulated in 2008 [9]. One of us (McBride) has been correcting for PT frequency-response errors off-line for some while, with excellent results. But none of this indicates routine use.

IV. STANDARDIZATION

It may as well be assumed that measurements are done by digital equipment. The capability and flexibility of measurement systems greatly exceeds that of analog predecessors. The technology has been shown to exist to inform the measurement algorithm of the parameters of the transducer, and have the effect of the errors reduced.

The process of informing the algorithm could be standardized, with the information transferred by means of the Transducer Electronic Data Sheets (TEDS) defined in [10].

Accomplishing this would mean that the characteristics of the IT would have to be described for the TEDS, a greater effort than merely certifying compliance. But it is a procedure that can be accomplished on a Type-test basis.

The process can go further. A modified TEDS could also store a recording of the output of the A/D converters in a measurement system used during that characterization. Applied to the measuring system, that recording should reproduce a result that represents the primary quantity. Thus, a modified PMU that could read from a file instead of from its internal A/D converters could perform a self-check on demand.

Recalibration frequency depends on the stability of the IT: transformers are usually long-term stable, but CCVTs often exhibit drift. If the transducer is changed or recalibrated, a new recording should be available in the TEDS. The

measuring system can use it to perform a self-calibration, because on playback, the same primary quantity results should be reproduced as before.

That notion levies a requirement on the characterization of the IT for the TEDS. The calibration system (including the A/D converters) that created the recording should have a test uncertainty ratio of at least four [11], so the self-calibration can be considered equally good. If that is done, a threshold for an out-of-tolerance result can be set.

VI. CONCLUSION

A system view of measurement shows that the technology exists to correct for some transducer errors in real time. The standards exist to support the method. Automatic system self-calibration following transducer replacement is possible.

If these steps were taken, measurement accuracy and device user experience would be improved, and greater confidence in the measurement system would be established.

The authors are considering proposing standard changes to the Instrumentation and Measurement Society.

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